

IMPROVING EDUCATIONAL EFFICIENCY WITH THE HELP OF TEACHING TECHNOLOGIES IN COMPUTER SCIENCE IN ACADEMIC LYCEUMS

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Abstract. *This article shows the tasks of modernizing the educational system in the teaching of computer science in academic lyceums, increasing the effectiveness of the lesson using new pedagogical, innovative technologies.*

Keywords: *modernization, innovation, innovative education, interactive, technology, technique.*

The development of the Republic of Uzbekistan is of urgent importance to establish an excellent education system based on the rich spiritual potential of the people and universal human values, as well as the latest achievements of modern culture, enlightenment, science, technique and technology. Education of individuals who are loyal to the idea of national independence, have sufficient intellectual potential, are capable of independent thought and observation based on the modern achievements of science, and the formation of a perfect system of training competitive, highly qualified personnel is an important condition for the development of Uzbekistan. In a society where science is developing rapidly, and modern information and communication systems and tools are widely introduced, the task of rapidly updating knowledge in various fields of science, as well as rapidly acquiring it, is being set before the students to search for knowledge regularly and independently.

In the implementation of these tasks, education can also be expressed using the concept of "modernization". So, what does the term "modernization" mean in the dictionary? What condition is described based on this concept?

Modernization(visually "modern" - modern, advanced, updated) - updating of the object in accordance with new requirements and standards, technical instructions, quality indicators is considered.

Usually, in the process of modernization, machines, tools, production tools and technological processes are updated. However, due to the development of science, technology, production and technology, society also moves from a certain stage of development to a more advanced stage. When expressed in a philosophical interpretation, quantitative changes turn into fundamental qualitative changes. M: the agrarian society in the Middle Ages turned into an industrial society with the development of science, technology, industry and production.

Social modernization means the transformation of society from a social system to an open civil society. On the basis of this type of modernization, changes of a general or private character occur in the social strata of society. These include, among others, updates in the field of education.

Modernization of the education system is the re-development or improvement of the existing mechanism in order to meet the social, economic and cultural needs of the society, its

demand for qualified personnel, and the individual's demand for quality education, to ensure the sustainable development of the education system.

This modernization, preserving and enriching the best traditions of training and education of a person, acquires a collective character, fully covers all areas of the educational system and serves to satisfy the need for the training of qualified specialists settled in the society. The following priority tasks are solved in the modernization of the educational system:

- to ensure that every person has equal rights to complete education and openness of education;
- achieving new quality indicators in the continuous education system;
- formation of effective regulatory-legal and organizational-economic mechanisms in the continuous education system based on the attraction of new educational resources and their effective use;
- development of the social status and professional competence of the employees of the educational system on the basis of the support of the state and society;
- increasing the role of participants in the educational process - students, pedagogues, parents and educational institutions in accordance with the principle of the educational system being based on state and public management.

In modern conditions, the priority directions of modernization of the education system are listed as follows:

- creation of electronic information-educational resources;
- coordination of existing and new technological forms of education;
- creation of favorable pedagogical and technological conditions for students' independent mastering of the basics of educational and specialized subjects.

In contrast to the careful development of the methodical development of the lesson that motivates the teacher to perform effectively, the educational technology is oriented towards the activity of the students, and it serves to create the necessary conditions for the independent mastering of the educational materials, taking into account the individual and joint activities of the students.

The central problem of educational technology- is to ensure the achievement of the educational goal through the development of the learner's personality.

Today, a widely used direction of education with the help of modern educational technologies is innovative education.

Lexically, the concept of "innovation" when translated from the English language ("innovation") means "introducing something new". The concept of "innovation" represents a specific situation in terms of content.

Innovation- activity aimed at changing the internal structure of a specific system.

According to the "National Encyclopedia of Uzbekistan", innovation has the following content and concepts:

"**Innovation**(cf. "innovations" - introduced innovation, invention) - 1) funds spent on the economy to ensure the replacement of technology and technology generations;

2) innovations in the fields of engineering, technology, management and labor organization based on scientific and technical achievements and best practices, as well as their application in various fields and spheres of activity".

Innovative education(visual "innovation" - innovation, invention) - education that creates the opportunity to create new ideas, standards, rules, qualities and skills related to the natural acceptance of advanced ideas, standards, rules created by other people. The technologies used in the process of innovative education are called innovative educational technologies or educational innovations.

Educational innovations- forms, methods and technologies that can be used to solve the existing problem in the field of education or in the educational process based on a new approach and guarantee a more effective result than before.

Innovative technologies are the introduction of innovations and changes to the pedagogical process and teacher's and student's activities, and interactive methods are mainly used in its implementation.

Interactive method- means to act and argue with each other.

What innovative forms, methods and tools are used in teaching computer science?

Brainstorming;

Work in small groups;

Ice cream;

Debate;

Cube game...

Methods used in personalized learning technologies:

"Brainstorming", "Cluster", "Decision tree", "Place the pictures correctly", "Video puzzle", "Staircase", "BBB", "Role-playing games", "Competition games", "Mosaic game", "Case study".

In fact, the information presented in the process of studying computer science allows students to form their own independent mind. The main goal of work aimed at improving the effectiveness of computer science teaching is to provide the necessary information to students in educational institutions, to form their independent consciousness, and to determine the factors for achieving high performance. Ensuring a positive solution to this goal requires the formation of a new approach to the improvement of the process of teaching computer science due to the vital necessity arising as a result of the deepening of the content of social relations and today's demand. A positive result of the goal aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the teaching of informatics, implemented in academic lyceums, requires the fulfillment of a number of pedagogical tasks.

Creation of objective conditions that allow teaching of informatics in academic lyceums at the level of current requirements.

Involving computer science teachers in training courses to provide information on the content of modern pedagogical technology theory and to acquire knowledge and skills on updated information technologies and programs.

Analysis of the current level of effectiveness of teaching computer science achieved in academic lyceums.

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